

A facile and one pot highly efficient synthesis of 1,3-oxathiolan-5-one derivatives

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Abstract : An efficient and effective method for the synthesis of 1,3-oxathiolan-5-one derivatives by cyclocondensation reaction at room temperature has been described. This method is an excellent way to obtain the title compounds in quantitative yields in a simple and cost effective way. Applying this methodology, different heterocycles possessing 1,3-oxathiolan-5-one moiety were synthesized.

Keywords : 1,3-Oxathiolan-5-one, cyclocondensation reaction.

Introduction

Heterocyclic systems are one of the most important classes of organic compounds present in nature or synthesized in laboratory. These compound posses several interesting biological activity. Indeed, one of the richest sources of diversity for the medicinal chemist are small heterocyclic rings, which in addition to often exhibiting biological activity, may serve as rigid scaffolds for further display of functionalities¹. Oxathiolan-5-one derivatives are of great interest because they exhibit a broad spectrum of biological activities and are important heterocycles occurring in natural and medicinal molecules. They are intermediates in the synthesis of many bioactive compounds². To exemplify, derivatives of 2-(hydroxymethyl)-1,3-oxathiolan-5-ones can be used as building blocks for the preparation of the oxathiolanylnucleoside Coviracil³⁻⁵. 1,3-Oxathiolane/1,3-oxathianes are one such class of heterocycles which have attracted much attention as they have been reported to possess a wide range of biological activities, including antiviral⁶, anticonvulsant⁷, antiulcer⁸ and antifungal activity⁹. In addition, they also showed anti-HIV and anti-HBV activity¹⁰ and oxathiolanes act both as agonists¹¹⁻¹³ and antagonists on muscarinic receptors. Cevimeline (*cis*-2-methylspiro [1,3-oxathiolane-5,3'-quinuclidine hydrochloride]) is a selective M1 receptor agonist.

A brief overview of literature showed that various

protocols have been developed for the synthesis of 1,3-oxathialane-5-one but they have various technical limitation such as long reaction time, difficult workup, and formation of over-oxidation products leading to lower yields, requirements of strong oxidizing agents, strong acidic or basic media, prolonged heating using benzene¹⁴ and the catalysts *p*-toluenesulfonic acid (*p*-TSA)¹⁵ the dimethyltin diiodide-HMPTA complex¹⁶, use of expensive, toxic, and explosive LiBr¹⁷, molecular iodine in [bmim][BF₄] ionic liquid¹⁸, zinc chloride¹⁹. Thus there is an inevitable need to develop an effective, efficient and cost effective synthetic procedure for synthesizing 1,3-oxathiolan-5-one derivatives which should be capable to overcome the above mentioned limitations. In continuation of interest on the synthesis of 1,3-oxathiolan-5-one derivatives herein an easy, practical and efficient cost effective, time saving procedure for the synthesis of 1,3-oxathiolan-5-one derivatives by using dehydrating/cyclising agent dicyclohexylcarbodiimide (DCC). In a general reaction, treatment of aromatic aldehyde with mercaptoacetic acid in THF in the presence of triethylamine and DCC afforded 2-(substituted aryl or alkyl)-1,3-oxathiolan-5-one derivatives with higher yields.

Results and discussion

In the present research work twelve 2-(substituted aryl or alkyl)-1,3-oxathiolan-5-one derivatives were synthe-

sized by using aldehyde and mercaptoacetic acid. In a general reaction, treatment of appropriate aryl or alkyl aldehyde with mercaptoacetic acid in THF followed by addition triethylamine (TEA) and dicyclohexylcarbodiimide (DCC) afforded substituted 1,3-oxathiolan-5-one in 92% yield (Scheme 1). Reaction required very short duration, 30 min for completion of reaction and gave better yield as compared to conventional synthesis.

R = Phenyl, substituted phenyl, substituted pyridyl, cycloalkyl

Scheme 1. General scheme for the synthesis of title compound.

This cyclocondensation reaction is two-step reaction. The first step involves nucleophilic attack of thiol group of thioglycolic acid on carbon oxygen double bond of carbonyl group of substituted aldehyde in the presence of triethylamine (TEA) giving the intermediate. Substituted hydroxyl thio acid which on elimination of water molecule in the presence of dicyclohexylcarbodiimide (DCC) gives substituted 1,3-oxathiolan-5-one derivatives and side product of DCC i.e. substituted dicyclohexyl urea which

is insoluble in water as well as in organic solvent that can be easily removed by simple filtration. The suggested mechanism for cyclocondensation reaction shown in Scheme 2.

Moreover, in general, the desired compounds obtained in a single step with high yield. This has been noticed so far, that the modifications on 1,3-oxathiolan-5-one moiety could display valuable biological activities and these modifications can be utilized to develop potentially active agents in future. Thus, the many more modifications on 1,3-oxathiolan-5-one moiety needs to be continued. An effort was made to synthesize a novel series of 1,3-oxathiolan-5-one derivatives of pharmaceutical interest by condensing the substituted aldehyde and mercaptoacetic acid. Thus series of 1,3-oxathiolan-5-one were prepared by using above discussed methodology which are shown in Table 1.

The structures of the products **3a-l** were established by spectral and elemental analysis. The structural elucidations of the products were based on their spectral (^1H and mass) data as given below.

2-Phenyl-1,3-oxathiolan-5-one (3a) :

Analysis Calcd. for $\text{C}_9\text{H}_8\text{O}_2\text{S}$: C, 59.98; H, 4.47; O,

Scheme 2. The suggested mechanism for the formation of the title compounds.

Table 1. Synthesis of 1,3-oxathiolan-5-one derivatives

Sr. no.	Compound	R	Product	Molecular formula	M.p. (°C)	Yield (%)
1.	3a		C ₉ H ₈ O ₂ S	88	86	
2.	3b		C ₉ H ₇ ClO ₂ S	134	83	
3.	3c		C ₉ H ₆ Cl ₂ O ₂ S	169	88	
4.	3d		C ₉ H ₆ Cl ₂ O ₂ S	165	87	
5.	3e		C ₉ H ₆ ClNO ₄ S	–	72	
6.	3f		C ₁₁ H ₁₂ O ₂ S	138	90	
7.	3g		C ₉ H ₇ BrO ₂ S	165	84	
8.	3h		C ₈ H ₆ ClNO ₂ S	181	94	
9.	3i		C ₁₀ H ₆ FNO ₂ S	184	77	
10.	3j		C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₃ S	130	89	
11.	3k		C ₉ H ₉ NO ₃ S	188	90	
12.	3l		C ₉ H ₁₄ O ₂ S	81	91	

17.75; S, 17.79. Found : C, 59.99; H, 4.49; O, 17.78; S, 17.81%; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃, TMS δ ppm) : 3.76 (1H, d, *J* 16.4 Hz, CH₂), 3.87 (1H, d, *J* 16.4 Hz, CH₂), 6.47 (1H, s, CH), 7.40–7.48 (5H, m); MS (*m/z*) : 181.

2-(6-Chloropyridin-3-yl)-1,3-oxathiolan-5-one (3h) :

Analysis Calcd. for C₈H₆ClNO₂S : C, 44.56; H, 2.80; Cl, 16.44; N, 6.49; O, 14.84; S, 14.87. Found : C, 44.58; H, 2.84; Cl, 16.47; N, 6.51; O, 14.86; S, 14.88%; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃, TMS δ ppm) : 3.78 (1H, d, *J* 16.8 Hz, CH₂), 3.90 (1H, d, *J* 16.8 Hz, CH₂), 6.48 (1H, s, CH), 7.41 (1H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz, CH), 7.797–7.824 (1H, dd, *J* 2.4 Hz, CH), 8.47 (1H, d, 1H); MS (*m/z*) : 216.

Experimental

Chemistry :

Melting points of all the compounds were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Thin layer chromatography was performed using TLC silica gel 60 F₂₅₄ Merck and spots were visualized by exposure to UV light. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded in CDCl₃ on a Bruker NMR (400 MHz) spectrophotometer in using TMS as internal standard (chemical shifts recorded ppm). The mass spectra of synthesised compounds were recorded on XEVO QTOF and Thermo LCQ Advantage Max Ion Trap spectrometers. Elemental microanalyses were performed on a Carlo-Erba 1108 CHN analyzer.

General procedure for compounds (1,3-oxathiolan-5-one derivatives) 3a-l :

To the ice cooled solution of appropriate aldehyde (1.0 mmol) in THF was added triethylamine (3.0 mmol) followed by addition of mercaptoacetic acid (3.0 mmol). After 5 min DCC (1.2 mmol) was added to the reaction mixture at 0 °C and the reaction mixture stirred for an additional 60 min at room temp. DCU was removed by filtration and the filtrate was concentrated to dryness under reduced pressure to get a crude product that was purified by flash column chromatography on silica gel using hexane-ethyl acetate as eluent.

Conclusion

We have innovated a relatively effective and efficient method for synthesizing 1,3-oxathiolane-5-one by using simple and cost effective reagents. Due to the simplicity

of the conditions, high yields and purity of the products, the above mentioned methodology should find utility inorganic synthesis. In addition, this method is safer; it avoids the use of toxic or hazardous solvents.

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